

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

While a good part of Central Europe is under water and other parts are experiencing or have experienced excessive heat or long periods of drought while Western Canada had its first two August snowfalls recorded in recent history, just to mention a few of the anomalies that we are observing, J.UCS is remaining, fortunately, a stable island: after two much acclaimed special issues on Knowledge Management and a special issue on Spatial and Temporal Reasoning coming up, this July issues demonstrates again the scope of J.UCS: from algorithms for communication applications to very formal aspects, also the "middle ground" dealing with UML is covered in this issue.

Enjoy it! And don't forget to submit good papers to J.UCS and, yes, we still need more referees! Volunteers out there somewhere?

Happy reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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